

GENDER FEATURES OF THE FUNCTIONING OF ENGLISH INTERJECTIONS IN THE SPEECH OF MEN AND WOMEN

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Abstract. The article is devoted to the study of the functioning of English interjections as signals of emotions in the speech of men and women belonging to the English linguacultural community, which seems especially relevant in the era of global emotionalization of the modern communicative space. The article is aimed at identifying interjection units characteristic of the speech of English men and women depending on the functions they perform. The study was carried out on the material of the book “The Diary of Bridget Jones” by Helen Fielding, which is given as a diary kept by Bridget Jones where she shares her thoughts and feelings on her daily life. The leading linguistic method in the study was the method of contextual analysis. The article identifies and substantiates qualitative and quantitative indicators of the use of English interjections in the speech of English men and women. Of all the functions performed by interjections, the most common is the emotive function, which is explained by the nature of interjections. In women's speech, the prevailing number of interjections performing the emotive function is registered, which indicates the unconscious verbalization of opposite emotions characteristic of women, while in men's speech, a greater number of interjections in the phatic function are noted. The study found that all registered interjections in the conative, phatic, hesitation functions and some of the most frequent interjections in the emotive function are gender neutral, since their qualitative composition in the speech of men and women is identical. The results presented in the article allow us to systematize the data on the functional orientation of English interjections used in the speech of English men and women.

Keywords: English interjections, gender features, functions of interjections, emotive function, conative function, phatic function, hesitation function.

ГЕНДЕРНЫЕ ОСОБЕННОСТИ ФУНКЦИОНИРОВАНИЯ МЕЖДОМЕТИЙ В РЕЧИ АНГЛИЙСКИХ МУЖЧИН И ЖЕНЩИН

Аннотация. Статья посвящена исследованию функционирования английских междометий как сигналов эмоций в речи мужчин и женщин, принадлежащих к английскому лингвокультурному сообществу, что представляется особенно актуальным в эпоху глобальной эмоционализации современного коммуникативного пространства. Целью статьи является выявление междометийных единиц, характерных для речи английских мужчин и женщин в зависимости от выполняемых ими функций. Исследование проведено на материале книги «Дневник Бриджит Джонс»

Хелен Филдинг, которая представлена в виде дневника, который вела Бриджит Джонс, в котором она делится своими мыслями и переживаниями о своей повседневной жизни. Ведущим лингвистическим методом в исследовании стал метод контекстуального анализа. В статье выявлены и обоснованы качественные и количественные показатели употребления английских междометий в речи английских мужчин и женщин. Из всех функций, выполняемых междометиями, наиболее распространенной является эмотивная функция, что объясняется природой междометий. В женской речи регистрируется преобладающее количество междометий, выполняющих эмотивную функцию, что свидетельствует о неосознанной вербализации противоположных эмоций, характерной для женщин, тогда как в мужской речи отмечается большее количество междометий в фатической функции. В ходе исследования было установлено, что все зарегистрированные междометия в конативной, фатической, гезитационной функциях и некоторые наиболее частотные междометия в эмотивной функции являются гендерно-нейтральными, поскольку их качественный состав в речи мужчин и женщин идентичен. Представленные в статье результаты позволяют систематизировать данные о функциональной направленности английских междометий, используемых в речи английских мужчин и женщин.

Ключевые слова: английские междометия, гендерные особенности, функции междометий, эмотивная функция, конативная функция, фатическая функция, функция гезитации.

INGLIZ ERKAK VA AYOLLARNING NUTQIDAGI UNDOV SO'ZLARNING FOYDALANISHINING GENDER XUSUSIYATLARI

Annotatsiya. Maqola ingliz til madaniyati hamjamiyatiga mansub erkaklar va ayollar nutqidagi his-tuyg'ularning signallari sifatida inglizcha undov so'zlarning ishlashini o'rganishga bag'ishlangan. Maqolaning maqsadi ingliz erkaklari va ayollari nutqiga xos bo'lgan undov so'zlarni ular bajaradigan funktsiyalarga qarab aniqlashdir. Tadqiqot Xelen Fildingning "Bridjit Jonsning kundaligi" kitobiga asoslangan bo'lib, u Bridjit Jonsning kundalik hayoti haqidagi o'z fikrlari va tajribalari bilan o'rtoqlashadigan kundalik shaklida taqdim etilgan. Tadqiqotda yetakchi lingvistik usul kontekstual tahlil usuli bo'ldi. Maqolada ingliz erkaklari va ayollari nutqida ingliz tilidagi undov so'zlardan foydalanishning sifat va miqdoriy ko'rsatkichlari aniqlangan va asoslangan. Kesimlar bajaradigan barcha funktsiyalar ichida eng keng tarqalgani emotsional funktsiya bo'lib, u kesimlarning tabiati bilan izohlanadi. Ayol nutqida emotsional funktsiyani bajaradigan, ayollarga xos bo'lgan qarama-qarshi his-tuyg'ularning ongsiz ravishda so'zlashuvini ko'rsatadigan ko'plab bo'laklar qayd etiladi, erkak nutqida esa, fatik funktsiyada ko'proq sonli bo'laklar qayd etiladi. Tadqiqot davomida aniqlandiki, konativ, fatik, ikkilanish funktsiyalarida qayd etilgan

barcha kesimlar va hissiy funktsiyada eng ko'p uchraydigan qo'shimchalar jinsga bog'liq emas, chunki ularning erkaklar va ayollar nutqidagi sifat tarkibi bir xil. Maqolada keltirilgan natijalar ingliz erkaklari va ayollari nutqida qo'llaniladigan ingliz tilidagi undov so'zlarning funktsional yo'nalishi bo'yicha ma'lumotlarni tizimlashtirishga imkon beradi.

Tayanch iboralar: inglizcha undov so'zlar, gender xususiyatlari, undov so'z funksiyalari, emotsional funktsiya, konativ funktsiya, fatik funktsiya, ikkilanish funktsiyasi.

Ongoing discussions about the problems of equality and inequality of the sexes continue to stimulate the development of gender studies in various fields of science. The transformations taking place in the English-language sociolinguistic context led to the emergence of linguistic genderology, which took shape in the late 20th century as an independent scientific direction.

Thus, for a long time, researchers have been interested in issues related to the processes of gender aspects of the euphemization of the English language; with the study of the speech behavior of men and women; issues of gender marking of different types of discourse are studied; linguistic units used by representatives of different genders are analyzed. When it comes to investigations on using interjection by men and women, Lakoff [3; 100] argued that women's speech tends to be more "polite" and "uncertain" compared to men's, and interjections are part of this. While her focus is on the overall speech characteristics of women, she touches on how interjections, as expressions of emotion, may align with the softer, more empathetic communication style often attributed to women.

Also, Cameron D. [1] looks at how men and women use language, including interjections, in a socially constructed way. She critiques stereotypical views of how men and women use language differently, acknowledging that interjections might reflect these broader social expectations but that the distinction isn't always as clear-cut as traditionally assumed.

Deborah Tannen discusses differences between male and female speech patterns, including how women might use interjections to signal empathy, agreement, or emotional engagement [5; 70].

The objectives of the study include identifying the functional orientation of interjections used in the speech of English men and women; establishing the most and least characteristic interjectional units for speech, depending on the functions they perform.

Functions of Interjections in the Speech of Men and Women

The members of the communication	Interjections that perform an emotive function	Interjections that perform a conative function	Interjections that perform a phatic function	Interjections that perform a hesitation function
Women	61%			
	43%	17%	26%	14%
Men	39%			
	32%	5%	42%	21%

From the data presented in Table 1, it follows that if the most frequent interjections in the speech of English-speaking women are interjections in the emotive function (43%), then in male speech they are interjections in the phatic function (42%). Let us highlight the three most frequent interjections in the emotive function in the speech of men and women. Thus, for the transmission of emotions, the interjections Oh (39% and 52%), phrases with the word God (Oh my God; oh God, Good God, For God's sake, etc.) (39% and 10%) are typical for the speech of both men and women. Let us turn to some excerpts from dialogues demonstrating the use of the above interjections in the speech of representatives of both sexes:

The pragmatic function of the interjection "oh" and phrases with the word God in the speech of men and women can convey different emotions depending on the context and intonation. Here are some common meanings:

1. Disappointment, regret, sadness—when a person expresses regret, for example:

Bridget Jones: 'What's wrong, Dad?' [4; 113]

John Jones: 'Oh, it's just . . . Sorry. It's just . . . I was hoping to get out of it too.' [4; 113]

Pleasure or admiration - can also be an expression of pleasant emotions, for example:

Bridget Jones: 'Oh my God, it's a miracle,' I exclaimed. [4; 119]

2. Awareness, when someone comes to understand something, for example:

Bridget Jones: 'Oh my God. So that's why she's gone off to Portugal with my two hundred quid.' 'She may well be further a field by now.' [4;138].

Another difference in the use of emotive interjections is that men use a typical set of interjections such as oh, God, well, Jesus Christ, while women's speech is replete with different units of interjections such as pah, durr, chuh, oof. Below are examples from the book "The Diaries of Bridget Jones" that belong to female characters.

"Friends?" Pah! The Enemy more like!" I shouted happily, tucking into another Silk Cut and a couple of salmon pinwheels. 'Bastard!' [4; 68]

Can I come up?' Burr. All right, then,' I muttered grumpily, pressed the buzzer and lurched back to the table. 'Bloody bastard.' [4; 68]

The higher frequency of interjections in the emotive function recorded in women's speech (43% versus 32% in men) is explained by E. Yu. Gette's [2; 56] assertion that women's communicative behavior is characterized by the use of emotional characteristics for the purpose of self-presentation, while this feature is not characteristic of men's communicative behavior (Gette, 2010).

The first place in frequency in the speech of men and the second place in women are interjections that perform a phatic function (42% and 26%, respectively), in other words, they use interjections to establish or maintain contact between the speaker and the listener. This is a communication function that does not convey information about the outside world, but rather serves to maintain communication, check understanding, or express readiness for further communication. In the speech of English-speaking men, phatic interjections are registered almost twice as many as in the speech of women. (46% and 26%, respectively). The most frequently used interjection in the speech of both men and women with a phatic function were the interjections oh (47% and 38%, respectively) and ah (17% for both sexes).

Mark Darcy: 'Ah. Really?' he said. 'I read that when it first came out. Didn't you find there was rather a lot of special pleading?' [4;13].

The next most frequent are interjections in the conative function, which are recorded more often in the speech of men than in the speech of women (21% and 14%, respectively). This group includes interjections expressing the speaker's will: these can be both imperative interjections calling on the interlocutor to perform a certain action, and interjections with which the communicant draws attention to himself and encourages his interlocutor to respond, thereby regulating the communication process. For example, with the help of the secondary interjection Shh, which is a reduced form of the interjection Shush, formed from the verb, the addressers of the message are able to encourage the addressees to shut up or speak more quietly. The interjection Shh is recorded in the speech of English-speaking men and women in small quantities. Here are some examples of its use.

Bridget Jones: 'You want a pregnancy test?' 'Shh,' I hissed, looking over my shoulder.

But the most common in the speech of both sexes with almost the same percentage is the interjection oh with the words dear, darling, look, listen and is used by the speaker to draw attention to himself. [4; 64]

Piggy: 'Oh look, there's Mark,' interrupted Piggy. 'Oh God, yah,' said Arabella, beadily. 'He's left his wife, hasn't he?' [4; 55]

The third place in frequency in the speech of men, and the fourth place in women are interjections that perform the hesitation function: 21% and 14%, respectively. Interjections in the hesitation function serve as auxiliary elements for the design of the utterance. In terms of qualitative composition, the

interjections of this group are completely identical in the speech of American men and women. These are interjections such as Um / Uhm, Uh, Well, Er. In the speech of women, the most popular in this function are the interjections oh, in second place is the interjection well, and in third place is er. In the speech of men, the most frequent is also the interjection uh (33%), followed by the interjections ah (20%) and well and um (13% each). Let us give examples of their use. As a rule, these interjections are used in speech in cases when a person feels awkward or guilty. When formulating thoughts, communicators use these interjections as connecting elements that fill pauses.

Mark Darcy: 'But that's exactly what they do, do,' said Mark Darcy gently.

Natasha: 'Oh well, I mean if you're going to look at it at that level said Natasha defensively. [4; 56]

Sharon: 'Is this your new girlfriend?' asked Sharon. [4; 16]

Alex Walker: 'Well. Huh. You know, she thinks she is, but we're not going out

Bridget Jones: 'Um,' I said, flailing for an excuse for being so angry. 'That was a horrible thing to do to a young whippersnapper, throwing your weight about and humiliating him like that at a sensitive age. [4; 120]

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